

San Gregorio de Portoviejo University: 24 years of commitment to training professionals in Health Sciences

Universidad San Gregorio de Portoviejo: 24 años de compromiso con la formación de profesionales en Ciencias de la Salud

Mario A. García^{1,2*}

¹Editor-in-Chief, *Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud*, San Gregorio de Portoviejo University, Manabí, Ecuador.

²School of Medicine, San Gregorio de Portoviejo University, Manabí, Ecuador.

*Corresponding author

Reception: 02-01-2025

Acceptance: 17-01-2025

Publication: 31-01-2025

Cite as: García, M. A. (2025). San Gregorio de Portoviejo University: 24 years of commitment to training professionals in Health Sciences. *Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud*, 2(1), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.36097/rgcs.v2i1.3160>

Dear readers:

Last December, the San Gregorio de Portoviejo University (USGP) proudly celebrated its 24th anniversary (Official Registry No. 229, 2000), marking almost a quarter of a century of contributions to the region and Ecuador's academic, scientific, and social development. In this context, we dedicate this editorial to highlighting the growth and consolidation of careers in Health Sciences, pillars in this institution's history, and future projections.

From its beginnings, the USGP has been committed to academic training in the field of Health, with Dentistry as the pioneer of this vision. As the first academic offering in this area, Dentistry laid the foundations for developing comprehensive training committed to quality and professional ethics. Over the years, this career has evolved to position itself as a national reference, with graduates who stand out for their technical competence and human sensitivity in their professional practice.

Following this legacy, the courses of Medicine, Nursing, Nutrition and Dietetics, and Advanced Technology in Comprehensive Aesthetics were incorporated, expanding the academic offering and responding to the demands of a society that requires trained professionals to address the challenges of public and private health. These courses have strengthened the institution's commitment to training competent professionals and fostered applied scientific research, consolidating a space for the development of technologies and innovations for the benefit of the community (Oliveira et al., 2024).

This commitment reflects the institutional vision in academic training and its determination to contribute to the comprehensive well-being of Ecuadorian society. A tangible example of this commitment is the university's dental clinic, a benchmark in dentistry students' comprehensive and practical training. The first clinic was inaugurated on September 23, 2002, marking a milestone in the institution's development. From its beginnings until its modernization on the current campus, the clinic has evolved to meet the needs of both students and the community. In 2006, practice areas were inaugurated, and in 2010, an operating room and a radiology area were added. This equipment guarantees that students can access practical and rigorous learning while providing quality dental services to the community (Molina, 2005).

The USGP has also strengthened health professionals' continuing education and specialization through a diverse and high-quality offer of postgraduate courses. Among them are master's degrees in Occupational Health and Safety, Psycho-oncology, and Teaching in Health Sciences, as well as specialties such as Pediatric Dentistry, Orthodontics, Dental and Aesthetic Surgery, Pathological Anatomy, Critical Care Nursing, Oral Surgery, and Management of Surgical Centers and Instrumentation. These academic offerings reaffirm the university's commitment to quality education and promoting research and practices that positively impact health systems.

On this 24th anniversary, we celebrate the trajectory of our institution and the impact achieved in training professionals committed to our population's social well-being and health. This anniversary motivates us to continue working with dedication and vision, reinforcing our position in academic training and generating knowledge that transforms lives.

This third edition of the *Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud* is a testament to our university's commitment to disseminating knowledge, scientific research, and health promotion (Galarza, 2024). On behalf of our entire university community, from the *Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud*, we extend special thanks to those who have trusted this institution as a driving force for change and development in the Health Sciences and Ecuadorian society in general.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

- Galarza, J. (2024). Lanzamiento de la Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud: un nuevo horizonte en la difusión científica. *Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud*, 1(1), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.36097/rgcs.v1i1.3096>
- Molina, R. (2005). *Historia de la Universidad San Gregorio de Portoviejo* [Documento electrónico]. Universidad San Gregorio de Portoviejo. http://librodigital.sangregorio.edu.ec/opac_css/index.php?lvl=notice_display&id=242
- Oliveira, D. A. dos S., Bernet, R. R., & Hoyos, D. C. de M. (2024). The transformative integration of university extension and education in communities. *Seven Editora*, 576-582. <https://doi.org/10.56238/sevened2024.009-037>
- Registro Oficial No. 229. (2000). Aprobación del proyecto de Ley de Creación de la Universidad Particular San Gregorio de Portoviejo. Tribunal Constitucional, 21 de diciembre de 2000, Quito. https://sangregorio.edu.ec/uploads/paginas/Ley_de_Creacion_USGP.pdf

Disclaimer / Editor's Note: All publications' statements, opinions, and data are solely those of the individual authors and contributors, not *Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud* or the editors. *Revista Gregoriana de Ciencias de la Salud* and/or the editors disclaim all responsibility for any injury to persons or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions, or products referred to in the content.